

Neural Network Application for Enhanced Oil Recovery Method Screening

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To my colleague of physicists in Machine Learning for Physicists 2020 Summer School

Background and Motivation

Enhanced oil recovery (EOR) is a widely used technique to gear up production from a depleted oil field. In the reservoirs, where the oil is located, the energy that drives the production is the pressure inside the reservoir. When oil production has been for so many years, the pressure inside the reservoir decreases much. Also, there will be the oil that remains inside the reservoir, cannot be mobilized by the pressure, thus cannot be produced. The use of EOR is to change some properties of the remaining oil, for example by decreasing its viscosity or decreasing its surface tension, so that oil can be flushed out, and the life of the oil field is extended.

EOR is categorized into several methods, that can be chemical or mechanical. To know which method is suitable for our field, we need to do a screening. During EOR screening, we need to consider the physical properties of the reservoir fluid (the oil) and the reservoir rock. In SPE-35385-PA paper, Taber et al (1997) mentioned nine parameters that are needed to be considered during screening. Also, he discussed nine EOR methods. The parameters and the EOR methods are presented in Figure 1 below. The EOR screening metric can be seen in the Appendix. In petroleum engineering, we always believe that humans do better than machines, so doing EOR screening is a straightforward task. However, I would like to inspect how a “neural network machine” can perform such this task as better as humans. That is why I carried out this mini-project.

Figure 1. (a) Reservoir fluid and rock parameters for EOR screening consideration, and (b) Methods of EOR (my diagram; information from Taber et al, 1997)

Methodology

In this experiment, synthetic datasets are generated. The synthetic dataset consists of two datasets, the first one is the training dataset, and then another one is the prediction dataset. For the training dataset, there are 245 synthetic field observations, and for prediction, there are 50. Each observation consists of 6 observed parameters (or feature), which are 6 of the 9 reservoir parameters in Figure 1a; they are oil gravity (measured in °API), oil viscosity (centipoise), oil saturation (w/w), reservoir permeability (milli-Darcy), reservoir depth (feet), and reservoir temperature (°F). In both datasets, the observations are divided into 5 observations from each EOR methods in Figure 1b; they are N₂ injection, CO₂ injection, hydrocarbon injection, immiscible gas

injection, Alkali-Surfactant-Polymer (ASP) flooding, polymer flooding, and steam flooding. The method of generating the synthetic dataset is using random fashion, keeping the values distributed in triangular, over a range of value that is described in the metric in the Appendix. In the training dataset, each observation is labeled with each EOR method, whereas in the prediction dataset, each observation is not labeled. In other words, this is supervised learning. Figure 2 below represents the statistical pair-plot of the synthetic training datasets using the *Seaborn* package in Python.

Figure 2. Statistical pair-plot of the 245 synthetic training datasets

Next, the neural network is built using the *Keras* package. The neural network model used is sequential, and the layer is dense. Based on the architecture shown in Figure 3 below, a two-hidden-layer with 6 input and 7 output neuron was experimented. The first layer has 100 hidden neurons and the second has 50 neurons. Both are activated using the ReLu function. The output neuron is activated using the Softmax function. The model is trained on the training data over 100 epochs, the loss function is categorical cross-entropy, which took a short time, about 5-7 seconds.

Figure 3. Dense neural network architecture for multi-class classification used in this case study

Results and Discussions

The training accuracy achieved after the 345 synthetic datasets were trained using the artificial neural network was 0.7492. Following the testing procedure to the 50 synthetic datasets, the model enough accurately predicted the EOR method “labels” to each of the datasets. Figure 4 below represents the history chart of the training accuracy and training loss. To assess this, I compared the prediction result by the neural network with my own EOR screening result. The model enough correctly predicted the labels based on the observation features. In addition, a dataset may have the possibility to fall between two EOR methods. This may occur because any of the features can predict two methods. However, instabilities were observed while iterating this experiment (results changed), but this instability was not too prominent. I believed that the training was still not achieving global minima. Additionally, I observed that when iterating this experiment and achieved higher accuracy (up to 0.85), the accuracy does not always represent better prediction results.

Figure 4. Training accuracy and training loss history after training data with the model

Suggestion for Improvement

As an engineer, I might not trust one hundred percent of the prediction result, given the existence of instabilities (not achieving optimum global minima) and the result that higher accuracy does not represent better prediction results. Therefore, I come up with four possible solutions and suggestions for improvement. First, training validation (using train-test split, grid-search cross-validation, randomized cross-validation strategy) could give us insight into how well the model will predict correctly all the training datasets, compared to its correct labels. Second, hyperparameter tuning is a widely used practice to search the best neural network parameters (activation function, optimizer, loss function, epoch, and batch size) to achieve higher accuracy and better prediction result. Third, to solve the problem of one observation can have two possibilities of EOR methods selected, it is suggested to produce the probabilities (e.g. Method A 55%, Method B 30%, Method C, etc.) instead of only one predicted EOR method. Fourth, employing another neural network model is possible to study how different NN models can improve the result. LSTM auto-encoder as a technique of “recurrent learning” network would be perfect to try.

Main Reference

Taber, J. J., Martin, F. D., & Seright, R. S. (1997, August 1). EOR Screening Criteria Revisited - Part 1: Introduction to Screening Criteria and Enhanced Recovery Field Projects. Society of Petroleum Engineers. doi:10.2118/35385-PA

Appendix. EOR Screening Metric Proposed by Taber et al (1997) in SPE-35385-PA

TABLE 3—SUMMARY OF SCREENING CRITERIA FOR EOR METHODS										
Detail Table in Ref. 16	EOR Method	Oil Properties			Reservoir Characteristics					
		Gravity (°API)	Viscosity (cp)	Composition	Oil Saturation (% PV)	Formation Type	Net Thickness (ft)	Average Permeability (md)	Depth (ft)	Temperature (°F)
Gas Injection Methods (Miscible)										
1	Nitrogen and flue gas	>35 <u>48</u> ^a	<0.4 \ 0.2 \	High percent of C ₁ to C ₇	>40 <u>75</u> ^a	Sandstone or carbonate	Thin unless dipping	NC	>6,000	NC
2	Hydrocarbon	>23 <u>41</u> ^a	<3 \ 0.5 \	High percent of C ₂ to C ₇	>30 <u>80</u> ^a	Sandstone or carbonate	Thin unless dipping	NC	>4,000	NC
3	CO ₂	>22 <u>36</u> ^a	<10 \ 1.5 \	High percent of C ₅ to C ₁₂	>20 <u>55</u> ^a	Sandstone or carbonate	Wide range	NC	>2,500 ^a	NC
1-3	Immiscible gases	> 12	<600	NC	>35 <u>70</u> ^a	NC	NC if dipping and/or good vertical permeability	NC	> 1,800	NC
(Enhanced) Waterflooding										
4	Micellar/Polymer, ASP, and Alkaline Flooding	>20 <u>35</u> ^a	<35 \ 13 \	Light, intermediate, some organic acids for alkaline floods	>35 <u>53</u> ^a	Sandstone preferred	NC	>10 <u>450</u> ^a	>9,000 \ 3,250	>200 \ 80
5	Polymer Flooding	> 15	<150, >10	NC	>50 <u>80</u> ^a	Sandstone preferred	NC	>10 <u>800</u> ^{a b}	<9,000	>200 \ 140
Thermal/Mechanical										
6	Combustion	> 10 <u>16</u> →?	<5,000 ↓ 1,200	Some asphaltic components	>50 <u>72</u> ^a	High-porosity sand/sandstone	> 10	> 50 ^c	<11,500 \ 3,500	> 100 <u>135</u>
7	Steam	> 8 to 13.5→?	<200,000 ↓ 4,700	NC	>40 <u>66</u> ^a	High-porosity sand/sandstone	> 20	>200 <u>2,540</u> ^d	< 4,500 \ 1,500	NC
—	Surface mining	7 to 11	Zero cold flow	NC	>8 wt% sand	Mineable tar sand	> 10 ^e	NC	> 3:1 overburden to sand ratio	NC
<p>NC = not critical. Underlined values represent the approximate mean or average for current field projects. ^aSee Table 3 of Ref. 16. ^b> 3md from some carbonate reservoirs if the intent is to sweep only the fracture system. ^cTransmissibility > 20 md-ft/cp ^dTransmissibility > 50 md-ft/cp ^eSee depth.</p>										